

BAMBOO BASED COMPOSITES FOR WIND TURBINE BLADES

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SUMMARY

This paper examines the mechanical properties of a bamboo-poplar laminate that is under development for use in large (MW size) horizontal wind turbine blades. The bamboo laminates were formed by hot-pressing alternating layers of bamboo with poplar veneer. Mechanical properties that are discussed include tensile and compressive stress-strain behaviour, fatigue life and fracture resistance of the laminate, under Mode I and Mode II loading. The strength, fatigue life and fracture resistance are compared to that of birch-epoxy laminate and glass-fibre epoxy laminates. General recommendations for the further development of bamboo-based composites wind turbine blades are also discussed.

Keywords: wind turbine, blades, composite, bamboo, fatigue.

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo has many engineering and environmental attributes that make it an attractive material for use in wind turbine applications. The development of high quality bamboo composites is an important step in the path towards the use of green materials in wind energy. Over the past year, a joint development project was undertaken by ICBR in China and Risø DTU in Denmark to develop and characterize a new generation of low-cost bamboo-based composites for wind turbine applications. This paper discusses the manufacturing process and mechanical performance of a bamboo-poplar laminate that that was developed specifically for use in wind turbine blades and for other wind turbine structural components.

MATERIALS

The laminate used in the feasibility study was comprised of Moso bamboo curtain mats separated by poplar wood veneer. Rectangular slices (strips), with a width and thickness of approximately 5 mm and 2 mm, were used to form the bamboo curtain mats. The wood veneer was obtained as 0.5 mm thick sheets. The laminate was formed by stacking resin soaked bamboo mats and wood veneer into rectangular panels followed by hot-pressing. A microstructure of a typical panel is shown in Figure 1.

TESTING

Monotonic tensile testing was performed on dog-bone shaped test specimens with glass epoxy taps (Fig. 2). Compression testing was performed in accordance with ISO 604, using a special test fixture developed earlier at Risø DTU for testing UD glass and carbon fibre composites (Fig. 3). Tension-tension and tension-compression fatigue testing was performed at a loading frequency of 5 Hz. Resistance to crack grow and defect tolerance are critical engineering properties for materials and adhesive joints used in wind turbine blade applications. To evaluate

the mixed-mode crack growth resistance of the laminates, double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens were machined from bamboo-poplar panels that were processed with a nominal thickness of 20 mm.

RESULTS

Results from the pilot study showed the feasibility of manufacturing bamboo-based laminates using low-cost bamboo curtain mats and wood veneer. The tensile strength of the laminate ranged from 175 MPa to 191 MPa with an average tensile modulus of 21.6 GPa. The compressive strength ranged from 105 to 118 MPa with an average compressive modulus of 21.9 GPa. The fracture resistance along the weakest orientation of the laminate was approximately 0.13 kJ/m². The strength, modulus, fatigue life and fracture resistance of the bamboo-poplar laminate all exceed those of birch. Further results will be available and presented at the ICCM17 in Summer 2009.

Figure 1. Cross section through hot-pressed bamboo-poplar laminate.

Figure 2. Tensile test specimen

Figure 3. Compression test specimen.